

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: PAUL****FIRST NAME: JEAN-MARIO****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. An Academic Essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-13)
2. The Importance of Punctuation in an Academic Essay (EUCLID 2021, 18-22)
3. A Need for a Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 41-42)
4. Chicago Style and Usage (EUCLID 2021, 47-56)
5. Plagiarism Ethical Problem (EUCLID 2021, 34-37)

THE FUNDAMENTAL STEPS FOR AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

After I finished reading the ACA-401/ACA-401D Roadmap (prepared by Professor Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma) and the Student Orientation paper of Euclid University, I hesitated to click on the word which is marked “start.” It was a pensive moment: a challenging time. A moment to know if I should engage myself or not. For my sake, at least, I might be asking myself questions about the consequences in the future because it was a point of no return in my life. I am a middle-aged person, and I have no time to waste. I must make a decision. I pressed “Start.” Then I said to myself, “I have begun a new journey.” Click on the word “Started” was a serious step to take. I knew that it would not be easy to pursue a doctorate study, but I took the risk as a winner. These are the reasons that I am embarking on this adventure; it is another way to discover a new world of knowledge and achieve my goal of having a doctorate in international law.

The coursepack (Period I), revised by Professor Cleenewerck in concert with Dr. Gulma, and the Basic tutorial video presented by Professor Cleenewerck are the

fundamental tools to start your academic essay, organize your ideas and write your response paper in the standard format of the Euclid University.

These fundamental rules for writing an academic essay reveal a formal and important issue because, without them, writing could be any other kind of essay except an academic one. As mentioned in the coursepack: “Academic essay or scholarly writing is nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 7). Therefore, in this response paper, my discussion will be set on academic essays, punctuations, plagiarism, style guide, and Chicago Style and Usage.

2) AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

In terms of rules and principles between many types of essays, an academic essay is the more demanding one. ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack (Period I) offers a basic principle of each part that constitutes an academic essay. Especially at the beginning of the first chapter, it is recommended to define and analyze the task because the principal purpose of an academic essay is to answer hypotheses that are supposed to be supported by the evidence. After all, these processes are a way to communicate ideas.

Thus the coursepack (Period 1) establishes a list of requirements that are considered the key to any academic writing: researching the topic is a technique to read and find arguments that will develop a thesis and answer; organizing your ideas is a time to draw up a plan for the essay and select the points that will be discussing like structuring the essay. The structure of an essay has a standard format which is shaped in three parts: the introduction, the body, and the conclusion. The introduction is a brief explanation that demonstrates the orientation of an essay and defines its essential terms. Also, it announces the important idea that will be developed in the following paragraphs of the body. This is the beginning of the discussion, where the evidence has been developed into argumentative answers to the principal question of an essay. Then, the conclusion comes as an inductive process that uses a particular specimen to make a general consideration of a topic.

Three elements constitute the basic structure of a conclusion. The first one is a summarization of the key points that have been developed in the whole essay. The second element is about “restatement of the answer to the main argumentative question” (Cleenewerck & Gulma, 2021, 10), and the third one is a final thought that gives the essay a vivid appearance and lets an opening area for a new horizon. Besides the rest of the suggestions that the coursepack (Period 1) has made, like referencing the essay, editing the essay, and handing the essay in, one of the most amazing and instructive parts is, to me, some rules of thumb for writing a paper.

The rules of thumb look like a summary of all parts that have been discussed at the beginning of chapter one of the course pack (Period 1). From the main thesis to the plagiarism section, it is suggested to the students to avoid all kinds of inobservance of rules and principles that could devastate a writing paper. The focus will be on the main thesis, which is a searching process that relates only to the relevant aspect of the writing paper, “anything else will be a distraction” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 13). Also, the

coursepack has excluded all kinds of generalities while clarity is defined as a pathway to differentiate poetry from scholarly writing. So, avoiding long paragraphs, and using appropriate transitions at appropriate times are the basics to keep the writing flowing. In the same way, unclear writing drives to a tedious, boring one. That is why redundancy, passive construction, and a bunch of preposition clauses are not recommended.

However, two subtitles of “the rules of thumb” which are “support assertions” and “do not plagiarize” express almost the same concern: the reference to the sources that are used in the paper's argument. The “support assertions” give a choice between quoting an important passage of an author or not quoting it. The general rule states that the only way to quote a passage is if it is a relevant part of a discussion. That means, in case that is not relevant to the discussion the students can choose not to use any. “Do not plagiarize” also links to the sources' issues because taking a word from a source without quotation marks is perceived as plagiarism. This can result in sanctions that could be severe, and they could, also, determine the failing or passing grade of a student.

Another point that has been discussed in this chapter is the seriousness of the students about the author's views. It is suggested that they take the views of the author as seriously as they do because the books or articles that they have to work on come to a sustained reflection. Their critics have to be fair and interpret the exact views of the author. A priori, the students should question themselves about the feedback of whom the critics are addressed. Doing so assumes that this person – the author – is not stupid. In other words, those who analyze and criticize these works have to be careful and argue with themselves before making any commentaries.

Throughout this chapter, it is explained that writing an academic essay takes work. It is complex not only for the concision and precision that is required but for the entire work that the students are assigned. I have learned that all the suggestions and details provided by the coursepack are important even to make a schedule arrangement. For example, the notice in the subtitle “Starting the Essay” is one of the parts that recommend starting on the essay as early as possible because, generally, writing requires time. Nevertheless, this is the first time I have, also, learned that I can opine in academic writing, which, I knew is supposed to be an objective and scientific approach. So, this experience made me understand that multiple surprises like that would occur during this doctoral study process.

3) THE IMPORTANCE OF PUNCTUATION IN AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

There is no specific definition of “Punctuation” in the coursepack of Euclid University. However, experts have defined “punctuation” as one of the most important methods to use to understand writing which should be clear and fluid (GPO 2023). Authors have to avoid ambiguity because the writing production is an indirect conversation between the reader and the narrator, and none of them would not have the opportunity to interact face-to-face with each other. That is one of the reasons that punctuation errors are

forbidden. They can cost pain and anxiety. “Dear John Punctuation” is one of the best illustrations of punctuation mistakes.

It is a story about a man who received a beautiful letter from his girlfriend. Throughout the letter, she expressed her feelings and dreams that could make him joyful, but the punctuation mistakes turned this love letter into a tragedy. Here is the letter that I have reproduced:

“Dear John, I want a man who knows what love is. All about you are generous, kind, thoughtful people who are not like you. Admit to being useless and inferior. You have ruined me. For other men, I yearn. For you, I have no feelings whatsoever. When we’re apart, I can be forever happy. Will you let me be? Yours, Jane” (BOU 2023).

This so-called love letter sounds awkward, but it is not. On the other hand, punctuation corrections will make it understandable and express the exact feelings that the girl wanted to convey to her boyfriend. At the same time, it shows the real need for punctuation in writing production, especially in academic writing. Here is the corrected version:

“Dear John: I want a man who knows what love is all about. You are generous, kind, and thoughtful. People who are not like you admit to being useless and inferior. You have ruined me for other men. I yearn for you. I have no feelings whatsoever when we’re apart. I can be forever happy—will you let me be yours? Jane.”

It is important to note that “Punctuation,” in essence, is a broadened definition. Regularly, it refers to punctuation marks that are used as a mark to separate sentences and phrases in a way to emphasize clarity and understanding of the writing activity. In the chapter on punctuations of the EUCLID coursepack, a group of punctuation marks has been listed and defined. However, I will discuss in this response paper the most common usage of them, such as comma, colon and semi-colon, full stop, and question marks.

In a sentence, a comma marks pause and separation. It is used after introductory adverbs, adverbial phrases, subordinate clauses, between multiple qualitative adjectives, and items in a list. A pair of commas can also be used to surround non-defining clauses, words, or phrases.

A colon is a punctuation mark that is used for many purposes in a sentence, like introducing a subclause, preceding a list, a quotation, and so forth. A semi-colon separates two parts of a sentence that are independent and related logically to each other. In a complex list, it could also substitute a comma to emphasize clarity.

As usual, a full stop is used at the end of a sentence, at the end of a reported question, or at a reported imperative. Finally, for a question mark, it is used for a direct question that is or is not in quotation marks.

I think nothing serious can be done in academic essays without clarity and comprehension. Moreover, punctuation reveals an important character that is a sine qua

non of being clear and comprehensive. And, I have considered that punctuation will be a meaningful aid in my doctorate study as well as style.

4) A NEED FOR A STYLE GUIDE

Like any company or product, every writer should have his original trademark that could be represented by words, phrases, paragraphs, sentences, citations, sarcasm, or vividness. Doing so requires intellectual and tough principles, which are supposed to be a solid style guide. For Euclid University, “a style guide provides a means of documenting basic rules or features of your writings that will allow you to ensure consistency in your writing output” (EUCLID 2021, 41). Unfortunately, this approach is far from a consensus. In theory, it sounds like a nice conception, but in practice, it is not realistic. Some writers still believe that style is an innate quality. There is no need for a guide style. Grammar and punctuations are enough to make the writing flow. According to EUCLID, this kind of idea is a nonproductive one; the style of a writer needs much more than grammar and punctuation.

The EUCLID perception of having a style guide to ensure consistency and clarity in the writing process remains a fundamental approach because the greatest achievements of human beings are always based on methods; nothing is given. The goal of the writing process is to communicate ideas and knowledge. Therefore, a universal method reveals a necessary tool to make the writing activity more accessible and easier to those who are dedicated to doing so.

I think the innate quality evocated by these writers does not exist anywhere because success particularly in the scholarly field has been always a result of hard work, discipline, method, persuasion, and passion. I, also, believe that style combines punctuation, grammar, documentation, consistency, practice, and art. The suggestions and academic tools that EUCLID provides to the students constitute an extraordinary help for those who pursue their careers in the writing field.

5) CHICAGO STYLE AND USAGE

Chicago style and Turabian style are one method divided into two versions. Both contain the same substances but are used differently. The Turabian version is focused on students' writings like response papers, dissertations, and theses, which will not be published and the Chicago style is for all professional academics, scholars, and editors who intend to publish (EasyBib 2021). Together they are a system ruling for documentation, sources, research, or rapport that should respect a constant, consistent policy and value in the writing process. In other words, the Chicago style and Turabian style are some of the best references to make academic writing. That is why Euclid University has stated that the Chicago style is the style of formatting books and research papers documented (EUCLID 2021). Moreover, this method has established the way that those rules should be used.

The EUCLID coursepack synthesizes the rules of Chicago and Turabian style that have proceeded with the usage. Though I will briefly emphasize, in this paper, two of the listed elements noticed by the University as needed to write an academic paper: Quotations and Chicago Footnotes. These two elements are a modelization of what is called the Chicago style.

A quotation is like a loan idea in a text used by someone who is not the principal author. It is considered a reliable source that is used to hence a precedent argumentation, and is related to the text by including notes, parenthetical citations, and citations (EUCLID 2021); (Camosun College n.d). However, the quotation rules do not admit indirect quotations, while direct and block quotations are permitted. Usually, quotations are tagged with quotation marks which could be single or double. They are followed by footnotes which are placed at the bottom of the page and include the author's name, book title, publication place, publisher's name, publication date, and the page number of the quotation (Douglas College 1991).

I never have been impressed by the complexity of the research method which is a variety of different approaches. During my Master II program at "LIMOGES University" in France, I thought that I would be able to face any existing problems in the research method even though I knew having some gaps with block quotations, commas, and footnotes which had not been discussed enough in the French approaches. Nowadays, I can say thanks to the video lesson, and the coursepack (Period 1) that allow me to understand and build block quotations without stress.

6) PLAGIARISM ETHICAL PROBLEM

"Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information" (EUCLID 2021). This assertion comes from the EUCLID coursepack (Period 1), which suggests several ways to avoid the plagiarism problem. The issue is not only a juridical matter about stealing an author's creation that can be sanctioned by law, but it is also a moral problem. A moral matter because the offender is a member of a prestigious corporation that deals with intelligent and conscious people. They know what they do. That means, by plagiarizing, they make a choice that is expropriating writers' creations. To exclude plagiarism excuses, Euclid University, through video classes and the coursepack (Period 1), promotes some rules as advice that can help students limit drift. Among the advice, some mentioned tips to limit the use of exceeded quotations. Those can be used to convince and create excitement which will drive the reader through the writing narrative, paraphrasing the author's information by rewriting it with new, and original words, giving the sources that provide the information, or the citation, etc.

I believe that plagiarism is a cultural characteristic that formats someone's personality into distractions instead of organizing his independence for the serious matter. It lacks courage and dignity (Plagiarism Checker X 2023). Euclid's advice boosts me to work harder on my writing performance and prepares me to face more writing challenges in the future.

7) CONCLUSION

As is noticed by the title, “*The Fundamental Steps of An Academic Essay*,” this response paper attempts to answer the problem that has been exposed in the introduction, which are the rules of writing an academic essay. I have said academic essay because, to me, there is no good or effective academic essay. Every academic essay is an effective one. Naturally, it is a mark of scientific writing that means automatically, it is immunized against imperfection. Saying that it is a good or effective academic essay sounds redundant. This paper reviews all aspects that the coursepack (Period 1) has developed from the first chapter to the eighth. However, our main purpose was to assign five concepts that are more important to me.

Those concepts are the writing of an academic essay, style, punctuation, plagiarism, and the Chicago style. The principal question is about the writing process of an academic essay which will be untasty without style, punctuation, and Chicago style guide, and could be destroyed by plagiarism issues. The way that I have documented and argued my paper could demonstrate that the punctuation chapter and Chicago style could be merged into one part, which is the style guide chapter because they are all connected.

I do not think that I have mastered the entire EUCLID coursepack (Period 1). I have some gaps that should be filled in, especially in the punctuation chapter, but I am sure by the end of the doctoral study process I will be able to do everything concerning the style, punctuation, and method of the academic essay.

REFERENCES

- Cleenwerck, Laurent and Kabiru, Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.
- Cleenwerck, Laurent, dir. 2021. *Basic ACA-401 Tutorial*. Vimeo.
- Cleeneweck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *How to Write a ResponsePaper*. Bangui: Euclid University.
- Pellat, J. C. and Fonvielle. 2017. Ed. Magnard. *Le Grevisse de l'Enseignant*. France.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.